

Investigating the Parameter Space of Potential Pulsars in Ultraluminous X-ray Sources

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Received _____; accepted _____

ABSTRACT

Ultraluminous X-ray Sources (ULXs) are unresolved sources outside of the nucleus of a galaxy whose X-ray luminosities exceed the Eddington limit for accretion-powered emission by a neutron star or stellar mass black hole. Such objects have been typically explained by either beamed emission or Intermediate Mass Black Holes (IMBHs), but recently, emission from the ULX M82 X-2 was found to have a 1.37 s period with a 2.53 day sinusoidal variation in the period, indicating that a pulsar is powering ULX emission in X-2. This is challenging to explain, since pulsars have only a fraction of the mass of an IMBH. However, the fact that such a system exists suggests that there might be other ULXs powered by pulsars rather than black holes. In this project, we take the first steps in analyzing this potential for ULX pulsars by considering the space of orbital parameters and determining for which section of the space the pulsar’s binary orbit does not affect its detection. We plot the calculated parameter spaces, and we find that we expect to observe pulsars with longer periods (greater than 10 s) much more often than observing those with shorter periods. We further find that M82 X-2 lies outside of this ideal region in the parameter space, and confirm this using XMM-Newton data.

1. Introduction

Ultraluminous X-ray Sources (ULXs) are unresolved sources outside of the nucleus of a galaxy whose X-ray luminosities, assuming isotropic emission, exceed the Eddington limit for accretion-powered emission by a neutron star or stellar mass black hole. ULXs have been generally found in star-forming regions of spiral galaxies, which implies that their

donor stars are O and B type stars, associating them with wind-driven accretion in high mass x-ray binaries (HMXBs) (Swartz et al. 2011). The typical luminosity range in the energy band 0.5 – 10 keV is about $10^{39} - 10^{41}$ erg s⁻¹. In fact, we can explicitly write

$$L_{\text{Edd}} = \frac{4\pi G m m_p c}{\sigma_T} = 1.3 \times 10^{38} \left(\frac{m}{M_\odot} \right) \text{ erg s}^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

where m is the mass of the accreting star (σ_T is the Thompson cross-section and m_p is the mass of a proton) (King et al. 2001). Thus, we require a donor star mass of at least about $M \geq 10 M_\odot$ in order to reach luminosities on the order of 10^{39} erg s⁻¹ and above.

It is not known definitively what powers these extremely luminous sources, but thus far, two popular models focused on beamed emission and intermediate-mass black holes (IMBHs). The theory of beamed emission posits that emission from ULXs may be non-isotropic, resulting in observations of a disproportionately high fraction of the total emission (King et al. 2001; Kuncic et al. 2006). Therefore, the actual luminosities would be lower than inferred. Through modeling, this theory can explain luminosities up to 10^{40} erg s⁻¹, but it cannot explain the most luminous sources (Kuncic et al. 2006).

On the other hand, IMBHs, on the order of hundreds to thousands of solar masses, seem likely as an explanation for many ULXs (King et al. 2001; Roberts 2007). The existence of IMBHs is still debated, since only stellar mass black holes, on the order of ten times the mass of the Sun, and supermassive black holes, millions to billions the solar mass, have been undeniably confirmed in nature so far. Nevertheless, there are likely IMBH candidates, such as HLX-1 (Farrell et al. 2009).

However, a recent study discovered 1.37 s pulsations in M82 X-2, a ULX located in the nearby Cigar Galaxy, implying that neutron stars may also power ULX sources (Bachetti et al. 2014). It is challenging to explain how a pulsar of about 1 solar mass could have a luminosity of over 10^{39} erg s⁻¹ using conventional models. Furthermore, the discovery indicates that pulsars and neutron stars may be more common among ULXs than previously

thought.

We would like to analyze archived XMM-Newton data to test the brightest known ULXs (which are catalogued by [Swartz et al. \(2011\)](#)) for pulsations. However, detecting pulsations in HMXBs is not easy, particularly due to orbital smearing. Orbital smearing refers to the apparent change in pulse period due to the Doppler effect and the overall motion of the pulsar. For a sufficiently large change over the observation interval, a simple Fourier transform would not be able to distinguish a clear periodicity, and therefore the pulsar might go undetected. There exist programs such as PRESTO which try to account for this unknown orbital motion by guessing orbital periods and folding the data, but doing so can be computationally expensive ([Ransom et al. 2002](#)).

In this project, we analyze the parameter space of potential ULX pulsars by determining the region in the parameter space for which orbital smearing does not matter. We would like to minimize the effects of orbital smearing, with the goal of analyzing actual ULX sources with XMM-Newton data to determine whether, or how likely, they are to contain pulsars. In the case that no pulsars are discovered, we can therefore narrow the region in the parameter space where each pulsar must be located, if they indeed exist.

2. Methods

In this section, we describe the details behind our parameter space calculations. We first describe the main parameters that we use in this project, then discuss two constraints for the system: Kepler’s Third Law and orbital smearing.

2.1. Initial Expectations

There are some constraints we can determine from previous work on X-ray pulsars (Li et al. 2016; Li and van den Heuvel 1996). We begin our analysis with the following parameters, with assumed ranges in brackets:

1. P_p , pulse period: [0.5-1000 s]
2. P_o , orbital period: [0.01-1000 days]
3. $a^* = a \sin i$, projected semimajor axis: [0.1-1000 R_\odot]
4. f , flux: [10^{-13} - 10^{-11} erg cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$]
5. A , pulse amplitude: [0-10 cts/s]
6. M , donor star mass: [1-30 M_\odot]
7. m , neutron star mass: 1.4 M_\odot
8. T , observation time: 100 ks
9. Energy range: [0.5-10 keV]

For pulse period (1), from the results of Li and van den Heuvel (1996) and Li et al. (2016) and taking into account the time resolution of the PN detector on the XMM-Newton, we find a scarcity of X-ray pulsars at the shortest periods, that there are only a few X-ray pulsars observed with periods of order 100 s, and that there are practically none at higher orders of magnitude. The same applies for orbital periods (2); the vast majority of X-ray pulsars lie in that range, and for both parameters the majority lie in the middle of each range (so we expect pulse periods of 1-10 seconds with orbital periods of 1-100 days).

For (3), we reason that the binary stars are likely not closer than about $0.1 M_{\odot}$, and their separation should have an upper bound – if the components are too far away, they would not produce enough emission to be a ULX. Nevertheless, the estimated constraints for a^* do not end up restricting our desired parameter space and have some room to be changed in further study.

The flux f (4) varies directly with the count rate R . The estimated flux range stems from the brightest ULXs known (Swartz et al. 2011), from which we use the PIMMS calculator to calculate the estimated count rate (discussed below in Section 2.4).

In this paper, we assume a sinusoidal signal of the form

$$x = A \cos(\nu_{\text{sine}} t + \phi), \tag{2}$$

where ν_{sine} is the sinusoidal frequency ($2\pi/P_p$) and ϕ is a constant phase. So, A (5) is in units of counts per second, the signal varying with period P_p . The assumed values come from a minimum of $A = 0$ and a high upper bound of 10 for the overall count rate we expect from these sources.

For donor star mass (6), we note that donor stars will likely be on the order of $20 - 30 M_{\odot}$, since an upper limit on the donor star mass is the maximal mass of a star producing a neutron star. Taking the neutron star mass (7) to be $1.4 M_{\odot}$ is standard.

For the last two parameters, the observation time (8) of $T = 100$ ks is about the longest that XMM-Newton can observe a source in the sky due to its orbit, and the energy range (9) over which is it most sensitive is 0.5-10 keV.

2.2. From Kepler’s Law

By definition, assuming a mass of M for the donor star and m for the neutron star, Kepler’s Third Law tells us

$$\frac{4\pi^2}{G} \frac{a^3}{P_o^2} = M + m. \quad (3)$$

From parameter assumptions 6 and 7, we find

$$\frac{4\pi^2}{G} \frac{(a^*)^3}{P_o^2} \leq \frac{4\pi^2}{G} \frac{a^3}{P_o^2} < 31.4 M_\odot. \quad (4)$$

Note that from this inequality, we can vary the donor star mass M to see how the projected semi-major axis a^* is constrained by the orbital period P_o for different masses.

2.3. Constraints from ”smearing”

From the velocity Doppler shift, we see that the pulsation frequency will vary with an amplitude of $\Delta\nu = \nu_0 K/c$, where $\nu_0 = 1/P_p$ is the rest frequency, $K = 2\pi a_p/P_o$ is the pulsar’s velocity, and $a_p = Ma/(M + m)$ is the distance from the pulsar to the center of mass of the system.

With this frequency variation, the power spectrum will appear (assuming a sinusoidal signal) as a peak widened with side lobes, over a number of bins given by $\dot{\nu}T^2$. In practice, this might appear more as a broadened peak with the width given by $\dot{\nu}T^2$. This ‘smearing’ will decrease the power in the peak of our Fourier transformation, making it potentially undetectable. Therefore, we must consider the math behind FFTs to derive a constraint on the pulse detection across the parameter space.

Note: If we assume a general observation time of $T = 100$ ks, that comes to about 1.157 days. In general, that should be a non-negligible fraction of the orbital period P_o . For reference, M82 X-2 has an orbital period of 2.5 days; using [Bachetti et al. \(2014\)](#)’s rough

estimates for the component masses and converting the velocity Doppler shift relation from frequency to period, we find a frequency variation amplitude of $\Delta\nu = \nu_0 K/c = 1.06$ ms, which agrees with their results.

2.3.1. Fourier Analysis

For the details behind Fourier analysis, I referenced [van der Klis \(1989\)](#) on “Fourier Techniques in X-ray Timing.” In this project, we assume a binning of $W=1$ and only FFTing (Fast Fourier Transform) over $M=1$ segment, i.e. the entire time series. Thus, to calculate the power needed for a detection, we have

$$\frac{\epsilon}{N_{\text{trial}}} = Q(P_{\text{detect}}|2) = e^{-P_{\text{detect}}/2}, \quad (5)$$

so $P_{\text{detect}} = -2 \ln \frac{\epsilon}{N_{\text{trial}}}$, where P_{detect} will be exceeded by noise only by a small probability ϵ . Here, N_{trial} and thus the ultimate power level for detection depends on the number of bins $N_{\text{trial}} = T/\Delta t$ we decide to use.

We calculate the power spectrum P_j according to the formulas for Fourier transformations:

$$a_j = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x_k e^{2\pi i j k / N} \quad j = -N/2, \dots, N/2 - 1 \quad (6)$$

$$P_j = \frac{2}{N_{\text{ph}}} |a_j|^2 \quad j = 0, \dots, N/2 \quad (7)$$

where N_{ph} is the total number of photons.

Now, if there is a detection, i.e. some j with $P_j > P_{\text{detect}}$, then we find the most likely value for the signal at j , which we can get by determining a level $P_{\text{noiselimit}}$ for which there is only a small probability ϵ' to be exceeded in one trial:

$$\epsilon' = Q(P_{\text{noiselimit}}|2) = e^{-P_{\text{noiselimit}}/2}, \quad (8)$$

so $P_{\text{noiselim}} = -2 \ln \epsilon'$. This then implies that

$$P_{j,\text{signal}} > P_j - P_{\text{noiselim}}. \quad (9)$$

The paper goes on to describe a method to determine an upper limit to the signal level if we do not have any “detections.” Define a power level P_{exceed} with a high probability $1 - \delta$ to be exceeded by any given noise power $P_{j,\text{noise}}$. So, that fraction will exceed the power P_{exceed} with no source signal, so we can comfortably say that $P_{\text{UL}} = P_{\text{max}} - P_{\text{exceed}}$ is a good upper limit for a signal, where P_{max} is the largest P_j we calculated. Alternately, for both calculating the likely signal power or upper limit if there is no detection, we can simply subtract 2 from the power, the average power of the Poisson noise.

In order to detect a signal to 5σ , we need a confidence interval of 0.9999994 – so only a 0.0000006 chance that a signal exceeds that power by chance. Now, P_{detect} depends on the number of bins N over which we search. We take the convention of choosing a time bin about a tenth or less than the period we would like to observe to reliably distinguish the different phases in pulsar’s pulse profile. For a minimum realistically detectable pulse period of 0.5 s, we thus want a Δt of 50 ms. Then, when we calculate the detection power level, we get (note that here, $N_{\text{trial}} = N = T/\Delta t$):

$$P_{\text{detect}} = -2 \ln \frac{\epsilon}{N_{\text{trial}}} = -2 \ln \frac{0.0000006}{100 \text{ ks}/0.5 \text{ ms}} = 57.67.$$

For Δt of 500 ms we get $P_{\text{detect}} = 53.06$.

We need to quantify the power that we expect from the pulsar. Recall that we assume a sinusoidal pulse signal. From the form in Eq. 2, we estimate the peak in the power spectrum of the signal to be

$$|a_j|^2 \approx \frac{1}{4} A^2 N^2 \left(\frac{\sin \pi x}{\pi x} \right)^2, \quad (10)$$

with a frequency offset from that of the closest bin j to the actual sinusoid frequency of the pulse ν_{sine} : $x = (\nu_{\text{sine}} - \nu_j)T$ (van der Klis 1989).

There is a relationship between the spread or smearing of the signal and the fraction of the maximum power in the resultant signal. Averaging over all possible phases and over the frequency offset x , we obtain Figure 1.

Fig. 1.— This plot shows the computed relationship between the peak power of the smeared pulsations and the number of frequency bins ($T\Delta\nu$) over which the peak is smeared, in blue. The peak power of the smeared pulsations is expressed as a fraction of the peak power if there were no orbital motion. The green dashed line shows the inverse relationship $P_{\text{spread}} = P_{\text{max}}/(\dot{\nu}T^2)$, taking $\Delta\nu = \dot{\nu}T$. The blue line is clearly below the green; therefore, the inverse relationship provides a reliable upper bound.

We notice that Fig. 1 is bounded by an inverse relationship. Note that we are trying to analyze the parts of the parameter space for which smearing is negligible in detecting the pulsation, therefore using a representative bound for a computed relationship is useful. So, we write $P_{\text{spread}} = P_{\text{max}}/(\dot{\nu}T^2)$, where $\dot{\nu}T^2$ is the number of bins in the power spectrum over which the frequency changes during the observation (i.e. so $\dot{\nu}T^2 = (\dot{\nu}T)/(1/T) = \Delta\nu/(1/T)$).

Note from Eq. 10 that the amplitude of the peak is approximately $|a_j|^2 \approx \frac{1}{4}A^2N^2$ close to the correct frequency ν_0 . However, this peak will be diminished by a factor corresponding to Fig. 1, which we approximate as $1/(\dot{\nu}T^2)$, and we also have to normalize for the power spectrum (i.e. $P_j = \frac{2}{N_{ph}}|a_j|^2$).

So, we get

$$P_{\text{detect}} \leq \frac{2}{N_{ph}} \frac{1}{4} A^2 N^2 \frac{1}{T \Delta\nu}, \quad (11)$$

so that

$$\Delta\nu \leq \frac{A^2 N^2}{2N_{ph} T P_{\text{detect}}}. \quad (12)$$

From this, depending on how T compares to P_o , we can express $\Delta\nu$ in terms of the orbital parameters as written above.

Putting actual numbers to Eq. 12, we have $T = 100$ ks, $N = 100$ ks/50 ms = 2×10^6 , and $N_{ph} = RT$, where R is the average count rate (we can estimate this based on the known fluxes of ULXs). If we consider the case that T encompasses the entire orbit, then $\Delta\nu = \nu_0 K/c = 2\pi a_p/(cP_p P_o)$, and we would get an inequality of the form

$$\frac{2\pi a_p}{cP_p P_o} \leq \frac{A^2 N^2}{2RT^2 P_{\text{detect}}}, \quad (13)$$

so

$$\frac{a^* R}{A^2 P_p P_o} \leq \frac{aR}{A^2 P_p P_o} \leq \frac{cN^2}{4\pi T^2 P_{\text{detect}}} \frac{M+m}{M}. \quad (14)$$

For our purposes (since we take the total integration time to be 100 ks) the right hand side only varies for different confidence levels. For the left hand side, for different choices of R , A , and P_p , we get various constraints for a^* and P_o . Therefore, we plot these constraints for different choices of these parameters to investigate the overall multi-variable parameter space.

2.4. Count rate estimation

The last important part of our method was to estimate count rate based on flux. Since the Fourier analysis depends on the number of photons we receive, we need a way to calculate reasonable values of R . So, we estimate the count rate using the [PIMMS calculator online](#) for the XMM-Newton PN detector. For our estimation, we used the Medium filter for the band 0.5-10.0 keV, taking Galactic NH to be $3 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (a typical value away from the Galactic plane) and the photon index to be 1.7 ([Winter et al. 2006](#)). Based on different absorbed fluxes, we found different count rates; for example, taking an absorbed flux of $10^{-11} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ yielded a count rate of 2.53 cts/s, while $10^{-12} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ gave 0.253 cts/s. For M82 X-2, we find a count rate of 0.8974 cts/s.

2.5. XMM-Newton data analysis for M82 X-2

Using the XMM-Newton archive, we obtain multiple observations for M82 X2 and the surrounding region. Using the Science Analysis System (SAS) suite for the data processing, we filter out the energy ranges 0.5-10 keV and 5-10 keV to compare the differences between harder and softer bands, and create power spectra to check for statistically significant peaks.

3. Results

Using Eq. 4 and 14, we can plot the parameter spaces in plots of a^* versus P_o . In Figure 2, we let the remaining parameters take on values specific to M82 X-2 as calculated by [Bachetti et al. \(2014\)](#). The one parameter with some uncertainty here is the amplitude A of the pulse profile, which we take to be $A = 0.008$ cts/s – there are no direct indications of this value in the paper. Therefore, the black line representing the smearing condition may similarly vary.

In Figures 3 and 4, we make similar plots of the parameter space for different values of M , A , and R . We also vary the pulse period from $P_p = 0.1$ s to $P_p = 100$ s in the four panels in both figures.

Finally, in Figures 5 and 6, we obtain power spectra of M82 X-2 and the surrounding region.

Fig. 2.— Parameter space plot with the parameters from M82 X-2. The yellow-green line represents the constraint from Kepler’s Third Law, and the black line represents the constraint we derived from smearing. The blue shaded region satisfies both constraints and therefore is the region where orbital smearing does not affect our detections. For X-2, the donor mass is estimated to be at least $5.2 M_\odot$, the pulse period is 1.37 s, and based on the observed flux of $4.07 \times 10^{-12} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and galactic NH of $5.04 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, we find an estimated count rate of 0.8974 ct/s. The position of the cross corresponds to an orbital period of 2.53 days and projected semimajor axis of $9.577 R_\odot$, as found in [Bachetti et al. \(2014\)](#). Since the cross does not lie in the blue region, we do not expect to find pulsations without accounting for X-2’s orbital motion.

4. Discussion

Figure 2 shows that M82 X-2 does not lie within the blue region. As we noted, there may be some variation in the pulse amplitude A , so the smearing constraint may similarly vary, changing the blue valid region. However, we note that in our analysis of the XMM-Newton data in Figures 5 and 6, we indeed find no statistically significant peaks near 0.73 Hz, which corresponds to the observed period of 1.37 s. This held even when varying the extraction radius and for both the full 0.5-10 keV and harder 5-10 keV bands. Therefore, we conclude that M82 X-2 does not lie within the region of the parameter space in which orbital smearing does not matter. Furthermore, from our constraints, we find that A has an upper bound of 0.01 cts/s.

We make another observation by examining the blue region for different pulse periods. In Figures 3 and 4, we observe a clear pattern. As the pulse period increases, the blue region gets larger and larger, implying that we expect to observe pulsars with longer rather than shorter periods in the ULXs. For example, for the extreme of periods on the order of 100-1000 s, the limiting factor is the Kepler relationship, but for shorter periods the Fourier constraint plays a much larger role.

With this analysis, we can analyze the brightest ULXs besides M82 X-2 to search for pulsations. We also aim to create simulations of potential ULX pulsar light curves, taking into account all the parameters we have discussed in this paper, and seeing how these light curves vary within different regions of the parameter space. By creating pulsation simulations, we may also vary the pulse shape and computationally find analogues for the theoretical constraints in this paper. Furthermore, we can compare the results from PRESTO to simple FFTs for these different regions of the parameter space using simulated data to analyze the sensitivity of each approach.

I am very grateful to Dr. Akos Bogdan, my mentor, and Dr. Marat Gilfanov for guiding me in this research project.

REFERENCES

- Bachetti, M. et al., 2014, *Nature*, 514, 202-204
- Corbet, R. H. D., 1986, *Mon. Not. R. astr. Soc.*, 220, 1047-1056
- Dai H. L., Liu X. W., Li X. D., 2006, *ApJ*, 653, 1410-1416
- Farrell, S.A., Webb, N.A., Barret, D., Godet, O., and Rodrigues, J.M., 2009, *Nature*, 460, 73-75
- King, A.R., Davies, M.B., Ward, M.J, Fabbiano, G., and Elvis, M., 2001, *ApJ*, 552(2), L109
- Kuncic, Z., Soria, R., Hung, C.K., Freeland, and M.C., Bicknell, G.V., 2006, *Proc. IAU Symp.* 238, 247-250
- Li, X.D., and van den Heuvel, E.P.J, *Astron. Astrophys.* 314, L13-L16
- Li, T., Shao, Y., Li, X.D., arXiv preprint arXiv:1605.03669(2016).
- Manchester, R. N., 1995, *J. Astrophys. Astr.*, 16, 233-244
- Ransom, S.M., Eikenberry, S.S., and Middleditch, J., 2002, *ApJ*, 124, 1788-1809
- Roberts, T.P., 2007, *Ap&SS*, 311(1-3), 203-212
- Swartz D. A., Soria R., Tennant A. F., Yukita M., 2011, *ApJ*, 741, 49
- van der Klis M., 1986, *Timing Neutron Stars*, 27-69
- Winter, L.M., Mushotzky, R.F., and Reynolds, C.S., 2006, *ApJ*, 649, 730

5. Extended Graphs

Fig. 3.— Plots of the parameter space as in Figure 2. In each panel, we take $M = 20 M_\odot$, $A = 0.02$ cts/s, and $R = 4$ cts/s. In each panel, we vary the pulse period: (a) $P_p = 0.1$ s, (b) $P_p = 1$ s, (c) $P_p = 10$ s, (d) $P_p = 100$ s. We observe that the desired region of the parameter space, in blue, becomes substantially larger as P_p increases.

Fig. 4.— Plots of the parameter space as in Figures 2 and 3. In each panel, we take $M = 30 M_\odot$, $A = 0.005$ cts/s, and $R = 1$ cts/s. In each panel, we vary the pulse period: (a) $P_p = 0.1$ s, (b) $P_p = 1$ s, (c) $P_p = 10$ s, (d) $P_p = 100$ s. We again observe that the desired region of the parameter space, in blue, becomes substantially larger as P_p increases.

Fig. 5.— Power spectrum of M82 X-2 with extraction radius of $4''$, centered on X-2. We used XMM-Newton data, with a total observation interval of 53.0 ks from 4/29/2009 08:23:21 to 4/29/2009 23:06:15, in the band 0.5-10 keV. We find no statistically significant peak near 0.73 Hz, which corresponds to the observed period of 1.37 s. This agrees with Figure 2; we do not expect to observe the pulsations directly.

Fig. 6.— Power spectrum of M82 X-2 with extraction radius of $20''$, centered on X-2. We used XMM-Newton data, with a total observation interval of 44.6 ks from 4/17/2009 10:38:35 to 4/17/2009 23:02:37, in the harder band 5-10 keV. We again find no statistically significant peak near 0.73 Hz, as in Figure 5.